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ADDRESSING AFRICAN FEMINISM

ABSTRACT

Reality normally precedes nomenclature. Charles Fourier coined the term “feminism” in 1837, but before and after then, Africa had strong women activists who were unaware of the coinage and yet fought for women’s concerns and their nations. It follows that the term “feminism” is not indispensable. Besides, the appellation neither fully represents the African reality nor aids the African struggle. African women’s concerns prioritize dignity, self-identity, fairness, equality and freedom, but fight against bad principles and structural injustices masked as traditions, the condescending attitude of men and white supremacists, hegemonic neocolonial economic theft, etc. Some African scholars have ingeniously formulated gender theories, and even a “feminist manifesto”. They have charted the course of and carved a niche for African feminism, but can they safeguard the sanity of the African people under the present dispensation? Dangerous feminist trends sweeping across the world are capable of wrecking moral values. Who takes care of feminist morality? The dictum, ‘there is something in a name,’ is true. If African women activists continue to bear the name “feminists”, people expect them to follow their Western counterparts to be firebrands and exhibit some level of recklessness. Either they join the bandwagon or be considered unserious. This treatise is a critical discourse that challenges African gender theorists to either discard the word “feminism” or establish *African Gender Ethics* as a watchdog to contain feminist excesses, and undue external influence.

Keywords: African feminism, Western feminism, LGBT, Gender theories, Women activists.

INTRODUCTION

Africa has always had strong women activists. For instance, when the British Governor, Sir Federick Hodgson, demanded the Golden Stool, a sacred symbol of the unity, strength, and soul of the Ashanti, Yaa Ashantewaa, the Queen Mother and Gatekeeper of the Golden Stool, mustered people and led the final war against the British in 1900. The War lasted six months, but the British did not capture the Golden Stool. Thus, the identity and dignity of the Ashante Empire were fiercely defended. Similarly, in the Aba Riot of November 1929, popularly known as the Women's War, thousands of Igbo women led by Madame Nwanyeruwa fought against the taxation imposed on women. About fifty women were shot dead by the British, and some others sustained injuries, but the taxation of women was not implemented. This successful protest heartened future Nigerian female activists like Chief Margareth Ekpo. As our people say, *Agu anaghi amu nwa ujo – The lion does not beget a weakling*. Funmilayo Ransome-Kuti also led women's protest against British rule, fought for equality, and inspired generations. Evidently, the link between women's liberation and the fight against colonial chains started from our foremothers.

If African foremothers could achieve huge successes without fighting under the banner of "feminism", it would be a shame in this era of dignity, for African women activists to shadow Western feminists, and engage in radical rascality just to be paternalistically branded strong feminists or be seen to have a strong voice in feminist agenda. For instance, it would be disappointing for them to champion LGBT (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender), advocate same sex marriage, and push for the abolition of state recognized marriages despite Africa's philoprogenitive values. African feminists are not obliged to copy every Western trend to the detriment of sane and sound values. Human freedom is not limitless, and it should be rational.

The West crossed the Rubicon when they legalized same sex marriage. The US leadership tried their best to ram it down the throat of Africa, but African leaders resisted it vehemently. It is not our culture; it is against our values, they said. When the Barack Obama administration pressed harder, threatening fire and brimstone, President Robert Mugabe of Zimbabwe quipped that Obama is very handsome, and he would not mind marrying him. This caustic sarcasm settled it, yet some African youths fell prey to homosexuality and transgender practices because they internalized the misguided notion that whatever is happening in the West is a trending fashion. If Africa had not been copying the West in other things, this rueful act would not have happened. Africans must not adopt every

Western *modus operandi*: concepts, methods, categories, and paradigms. They must not follow the footsteps of Western feminists. If to be a feminist means toadying and implementing things like LGBT, then African “feminists” had better think twice. Our ancestors said: Should the rat follow the lizard to play in the rain, when the lizard emerges with dry skin, the rat would be wet and shivering. When the West would have realized the mistake and reversed the legality of illegalities, they would have at their disposal ample means of remediation, which would not be available to Africans. If they dwindle their human capital, for instance, they have substitutes - highly productive industrial machines that have more productive capacity than humans. When they dull the brains of their citizens due to disuse, Artificial Intelligence (AI) will think and make decisions for them and fight their wars. AI even teaches in their classrooms and performs surgical operations in their hospitals. Should they want to repopulate their states, they will have at their disposal ectolife, human cloning, IVF, surrogacy, etc., things Africa can ill afford, not because Africa is poor but because Africa is kept destitute for ulterior motives. So, should African feminists destroy our values to pass for strong feminists, what remedy will be available to Africa when the chips are down? Fortunately, by their principled action of resisting external interference and pressure, the assertive African leaders made history, claimed Africa’s sovereignty and dignity, protected Africa’s interest, and reset the stage of global power dynamics on how the world engages with Africa. This paper is intended as a rethink for some African women liberation activists, who need to be extremely cautious.

AFRICAN GENDER THEORIES

African gender discourse transcends the frameworks of Western feminism to formulate theories rooted in indigenous cosmologies, epistemologies, socio-cultural contexts, and historical experiences. Instead of being acolytes of Eurocentric feminism, African female activists created nuanced gender paradigms that address the realities of African women, realities borne out of the experience of some deep-rooted structural injustices masked as tradition, indigenous values, colonial and neo-colonial influences, ecological interdependence, etc. African gender theories such as Womanism, Motherism, Femalism, Stiwanism, Snail-Sense Feminism, Ubuntu Feminism, Nego-Feminism, Femocracy, and Gynist philosophy, as alternative frameworks to Western feminism, models of agency, resilience, and social transformation, symbolize theoretical resistance to imported ideologies. They symbolise a commitment to reconstructing African societies in ways that promote identity,

dignity, justice, and gender complementarity. African gender theories underline the issues of uniqueness, power structure, rational culture, and the ethics of liberation. These theories challenge us to seek gender justice in ways that are culturally grounded, socially responsible, and epistemically inclusive. They distance themselves from the imitation of hostile, coercive cum violent extreme models that ignore the golden mean. This strategic thinking, which prioritizes African values, symbolizes intellectual liberation or mental decolonization, assertive agency, and a departure from the established order of paternalistic engagement with the West.

1) Womanism

Womanism is a term coined by the African American author Alice Walker, and later adopted and adapted by African feminist scholars to articulate a more culturally grounded and inclusive approach to gender discourse. Originally defined in *In Search of Our Mothers' Gardens* (1983), Walker conceived womanism as a social theory rooted in the experiences of Black women, emphasizing their capacity for struggle, self-definition, and community building. Unlike mainstream Western feminism, which often centres on individualism and sometimes antagonism toward men, womanism emphasizes the interconnectedness of race, gender, class, and cultural identity, particularly within African and African diasporic contexts. Walker described a womanist as “a black feminist or feminist of colour” who appreciates women's culture and is committed to the survival and wholeness of entire people, male and female alike.”¹

Chikwenye Okonjo Ogunyemi redefined womanism in African contexts, highlighting its relevance to African women's realities. She argues that African womanism centres on motherhood, marriage, communalism, and spirituality. It seeks to improve the status of women without destabilizing traditional structures entirely.² This approach critiques the failure of Western feminism to consider racial and cultural specificities. Instead of adopting a confrontational stance, African womanism proposes complementarity between men and women, recognizing both as partners in development, social transformation and human flourishing.

¹ Alice Walker, *In Search of Our Mothers' Gardens: Womanist Prose* (San Diego: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich, 1983), p. xi.

² Chikwenye Okonjo Ogunyemi, “Womanism: The Dynamics of the Contemporary Black Female Novel in English,” *Signs* 11, no. 1 (1985): pp. 63–80.

However, the womanist theory is majorly criticised for being potentially conservative. By prioritizing family cohesion and community stability uncritically, it may unwittingly reinforce patriarchal norms. Amina Mama, for example, challenges African gender theories that fail to confront structural inequalities directly, arguing that compromise-based frameworks often silence necessary resistance.³

2) Stiwanism

Stiwanism, an acronym for “Social Transformation Including Women in Africa,” was developed by Nigerian feminist scholar Molaria Ogundipe as a response to the inadequacies of Western feminism in addressing the lived realities of African women. It seeks to situate gender discourse within the broader socio-political and economic challenges of African societies. Ogundipe argues that African women face a six-fold oppression: gender, class, race, culture, religion, and colonial legacies, and therefore cannot adopt feminist models that ignore these intersections.⁴

Stiwanism rejects the blanket application of Western feminist categories and advocates instead for a transformational approach that incorporates African women into the rebuilding of society. It emphasizes active female participation in political, educational, and economic spheres, not merely as beneficiaries but as contributors and agents of change. Unlike liberal feminism, which often underscores individual rights, Stiwanism insists on collective empowerment grounded in African values and realities. Ogundipe stresses the need to focus on inclusion in development policies, equitable access to resources, and recognition of women’s traditional and modern roles in nation-building.⁵ Stiwanism’s significance stems from its commitment to contextuality. It does not separate women’s issues from national and continental development agendas. Rather than framing men as adversaries, it promotes cooperation for the mutual benefit of all genders.

Despite its strengths, Stiwanism is not immune to critique. One concern is its conceptual vagueness. While it provides a valuable framework for inclusive transformation, it lacks detailed implementation strategies, particularly regarding

³ Amina Mama, “Feminism or Femocracy? State Feminism and Democratisation in Nigeria,” *Africa Development* 20, no. 1 (1995): pp. 37–58.

⁴ Molaria Ogundipe-Leslie, “Stiwanism: Feminism in an African Context,” in *Re-Creating Ourselves: African Women & Critical Transformations*, ed. Molaria Ogundipe-Leslie (Trenton: Africa World Press, 1994), pp. 229–241.

⁵ Molaria Ogundipe-Leslie, “Stiwanism: Feminism in an African Context,” p. 230.

resistance to patriarchal institutions entrenched in both state and customary systems. Amina Mama notes that models of African feminism must not only call for inclusion but must confront and dismantle oppressive power structures that marginalize women politically and economically.⁶ Moreover, while Stiwanism advocates inclusion, it may risk assimilation of patriarchal values if it does not adequately address the systemic roots of exclusion. Inclusion without structural transformation can render women's presence symbolic rather than substantive. The concept must therefore be coupled with rigorous political engagement and legal reforms that ensure meaningful participation, not mere tokenism.

3) Motherism

Catherine Acholonu, a Nigerian intellectual formulated Motherism as an African-centred alternative to Western feminism. Motherism is a holistic and ecological ideology embedded in the nurturing principle of motherhood, It perceives peace, love, and tolerance as central to gender relations and social transformation. Acholonu proposes that through their reproductive and nurturing roles, African women hold unique capacities to foster communal harmony and national development.⁷ Unlike Western feminism, which is often characterized by confrontation and a focus on gender-based autonomy, motherism emphasizes complementarity between the sexes and the centrality of family and cultural values.

Its rootedness in African cultural and cosmological systems seeks to elevate traditional African values around womanhood, fertility, and care ethics, offering a model of empowerment that does not require the dismantling of existing communal structures. By grounding gender discourse in African realities, motherism resists cultural imperialism and affirms indigenous knowledge systems. Acholonu argues that women should champion ecological sustainability and social harmony through their natural roles as life-givers and caregivers, situating womanhood within a broader environmental and spiritual framework.⁸

However, motherism is criticized for seemingly romanticizing women's roles, reducing them to biological and emotional functions, thereby limiting women's political and intellectual agency. By centring womanhood primarily around reproduction and motherhood, motherism may inadvertently reinforce

⁶ Mama, "Feminism or Femocracy? State Feminism and Democratisation in Nigeria," p. 38.

⁷ Catherine Acholonu, *Motherism: The Afrocentric Alternative to Feminism* (Owerri: Afa Publications, 1995), p. 8.

⁸ Acholonu, *Motherism: The Afrocentric Alternative to Feminism*, p. 16.

the very patriarchal structures it seeks to reset. This essentialist view does not take into consideration the diversity of African women's experiences, especially those of the unmarried, the childless, and women who reject traditional gender roles. This marks motherism as not all-embracing.

Motherism's emphasis on peace and non-confrontation is equally critiqued for lacking a rigorous framework for resistance against gender-based oppression. Models of this nature are criticized for circumventing the need to challenge institutionalized inequality and for failing to account for the structural dimensions of patriarchy in African societies. Merely advocating nurturing roles does not provide sufficient tools for liberation or justice in settings where violence and legal exclusion persist because one must be alive before one can nurture. Here lies the wisdom of the philosophical dictum, *Prima vivere deinde philosophari*.

4) Femocracy

A Nigerian scholar, Amina Mama, propounded Femocracy to critique state-driven models of feminism in postcolonial African contexts. It refers to governments' appointment of women to political positions to project an image of gender inclusivity, whereas real power remains centralized and patriarchal. Mama's concept is particularly aimed at exposing how African states use women as symbolic figures in governance without meaningful empowerment or structural transformation.⁹ According to Mama, femocracy often operates within authoritarian regimes, where women's inclusion in leadership is dictated from the top and disconnected from grassroots feminist movements. This practice results in what she calls "state feminism," a model where women's political visibility does not translate into gender equity or broader policy reforms. These women, typically elite and loyal to the regime, function more as instruments of power consolidation than agents of feminist change.¹⁰

A key problem with femocracy is its tokenistic character. It allows the state to claim gender progress while avoiding substantive commitments to justice and equality. Women appointed under femocratic systems rarely challenge patriarchal norms; instead, they often reproduce them to maintain their privileged positions. As such, femocracy masks the absence of genuine gender-sensitive governance behind a façade of representation. It serves political expediency

⁹ Amina Mama, "Feminism or Femocracy? State Feminism and Democratisation in Nigeria," *Africa Development* 20, no. 1 (1995): pp. 37–58.

¹⁰ Amina Mama, "Feminism or Femocracy? State Feminism and Democratisation in Nigeria," p. 40.

rather than feminist ideals. Moreover, femocracy disconnects feminist activism from the lived experiences of ordinary women. Since appointments are often made from a narrow pool of educated and politically connected women, the voices of rural, poor, and marginalized women are excluded. Thus, Femocracy raises concerns about class and exclusion. This elitism challenges the democratic ideal that feminism should serve all women, not just a select few. However, it is important to note that the critique of femocracy does not negate the importance of women in governance. Rather, it calls for more democratic and participatory approaches to feminist politics in Africa. For inclusion to be meaningful, it must come with accountability, policy influence, and genuine advocacy for gender equity.

5) Femalism

Femalism advanced by a Nigerian literary scholar, Chioma Opara, is an African feminist framework that foregrounds the female body, sexuality, and psychological experience as central themes in gender discourse and literary analysis. Rooted in the African postcolonial condition, femalism addresses the intersection of gender, trauma, and cultural identity, especially in contexts where women have suffered the compounded effects of patriarchy and colonial violence. Opara defines femalism as a theory that emphasizes the corporeal and emotional realities of African women, asserting that the female body is a site of both suffering and resistance.¹¹ Unlike Western feminist theories that often emphasize legal rights or economic equality, femalism gives prominence to bodily autonomy and the psychic trauma women endure due to socio-political repression. It highlights how literature, especially women's writing, becomes a space for the articulation of this trauma. Through narrative expressions of pain, desire, and silence, African female writers recover the voice of the wounded woman and reclaim agency over the violated body. As Opara notes, femalism brings the female body "from the margins of discourse into a centre of meaning."¹² In sum, femalism contributes a necessary emotional and corporeal dimension to African gender discourse.

However, its strength in emphasizing embodied experience can also be viewed as a limitation. Critics argue that by focusing heavily on biological and emotional narratives, it risks essentializing womanhood and reinforcing the notion that women are defined primarily by their capacity to feel pain or nurture.

¹¹ Chioma Opara, *Her Mother's Daughter: The African Writer as Woman* (Port Harcourt: University of Port Harcourt Press, 2004), p.10.

¹² Chioma Opara, *Her Mother's Daughter: The African Writer as Woman*, p.12.

Furthermore, though crucial, femalism's emphasis on trauma needs to be balanced with structural and institutional critiques if it is to contribute meaningfully to broader conversations on gender justice and development. Its future relevance will depend on how it expands its scope beyond literature to engage with policy, law, and activism in practical terms.

6) Nego-Feminism

Nego-feminism was coined by a Nigerian scholar, Obioma Nnaemeka, to offer a distinctly African feminist framework centred on negotiation, collaboration, and cultural sensitivity. Short for “negotiated feminism” or “no-go feminism,” this theory emphasizes the strategic use of dialogue and compromise in addressing gender inequalities within African societies. Rather than adopting adversarial methods, Nego-feminism promotes relational approaches that recognize the interconnectedness of family, community, and social harmony.¹³ It highlights the belief that African women have historically exercised agency not through confrontation but through tactful negotiation within patriarchal structures. Nnaemeka contends that African feminist thought must reflect the complex socio-cultural realities in which women operate, particularly in societies where communal values and extended kinship systems are central to identity and power.¹⁴ This approach enables women to pursue empowerment without alienating male allies or disrupting social cohesion.

One of the key strengths of Nego-feminism is its rejection of rigid ideological categories. It does not seek to mimic Western feminism, which often emphasizes individual autonomy and legal equality. Instead, it offers a flexible model that accommodates both tradition and transformation. Nego-feminism is grounded in praxis, drawing from women’s lived experiences of balancing resistance with responsibility. It affirms that feminist action in Africa must be both culturally rooted and politically strategic.

However, this model is not without criticism. Some scholars argue that Nego-feminism’s emphasis on negotiation may underplay the urgency and severity of structural gender-based oppression. Approaches focused on compromise may result in accommodation rather than genuine liberation, especially when confronting institutions that are deeply invested in patriarchal

¹³ Obioma Nnaemeka, “Nego-Feminism: Theorizing, Practicing, and Pruning Africa’s Way,” *Signs* 29, no. 2 (2004): pp. 357–385.

¹⁴ Obioma Nnaemeka, “Nego-Feminism: Theorizing, Practicing, and Pruning Africa’s Way,” p.362.

dominance. By relying heavily on diplomacy, Nego-feminism may risk legitimizing systems that perpetuate inequality. Furthermore, Nego-feminism may be more accessible to women with social capital, education, or positional influence, while less effective for those whose marginalization leaves little room for negotiation. Critics also question whether certain forms of violence, such as domestic abuse or state-sponsored repression, can be addressed adequately through strategies of compromise and negotiation.

7) Snail-Sense Feminism

Snail-sense feminism, developed by a Nigerian scholar Akachi Adimora-Ezeigbo, is a pragmatic feminist framework that advocates for gradual, strategic, and context-sensitive approaches to gender relations in Africa. Drawing its metaphor from the snail's slow but determined movement, the theory promotes non-confrontational methods of negotiation, adaptability, and resilience. Adimora-Ezeigbo argues that the snail's ability to navigate difficult terrains while protecting its soft body with a shell illustrates the survival strategies employed by African women in patriarchal societies.¹⁵ The central thrust of snail-sense feminism lies in its recognition of cultural realities. Rather than confronting patriarchal systems head-on, it encourages women to adopt indirect and diplomatic methods to assert agency. This includes leveraging tradition, appealing to communal values, and working within existing structures to achieve social change. She contends that such an approach avoids social fragmentation and facilitates long-term transformation without alienating male allies or destabilizing communities.¹⁶

One of the key strengths of snail-sense feminism is its cultural rootedness. It aligns with the African worldview that values communal harmony, respect for elders, and strategic adaptability. It also reflects the lived realities of many African women who, despite systemic oppression, navigate patriarchal settings with tact and subtle resistance. However, snail-sense feminism has attracted criticism for its perceived conservatism. By emphasizing caution and compromise, it may inadvertently validate and sustain patriarchal norms rather than challenge them. In contexts where gender-based violence and exclusion are entrenched, subtle strategies may not be sufficient to address deep structural inequalities. Moreover, while snail-sense feminism offers a culturally sensitive mode of resistance, it risks essentializing African women as inherently patient

¹⁵ Akachi Adimora-Ezeigbo, *Snail-Sense Feminism: Building on an Indigenous Model* (Lagos: University of Lagos Press, 2012), p.16.

¹⁶ Adimora-Ezeigbo, *Snail-Sense Feminism: Building on an Indigenous Model*, p.18.

and diplomatic, thereby limiting the scope for assertive forms of activism. It does not adequately account for the diversity of African women's experiences, especially those who choose more vocal or disruptive forms of engagement. As our people say, unless a bachelor behaves like a madman, his people will not marry a wife for him.

8) Ubuntu Feminism

Ubuntu Feminism, as articulated by Drucilla Cornell and Karin van Marle, is grounded in the South African philosophical tradition of *ubuntu*, which centres on humanity, interconnectedness, and communal responsibility. Unlike liberal feminist frameworks that prioritize individual autonomy, Ubuntu Feminism views the individual as fundamentally embedded in a network of relationships. It emphasizes that gender justice cannot be achieved without a collective commitment to restoring dignity, nurturing solidarity, and rehumanizing social relations.¹⁷ At its core, Ubuntu Feminism insists that equality is not merely a legal status but a lived ethical practice that involves treating others with compassion and respect. Cornell and Van Marle argue that the communal values of *ubuntu* provide a unique foundation for feminist thought in post-apartheid South Africa, where social fragmentation and historical injustice continue to affect women disproportionately.¹⁸ Within this framework, gender equality is not pursued through adversarial means but through restoring relational harmony and mutual recognition.

One of the key strengths of Ubuntu Feminism lies in its emphasis on relational ethics. It does not isolate gender from broader questions of social justice, human dignity, and moral responsibility. Instead, it promotes an integrated approach that challenges both patriarchal domination and alienating legalism. In this sense, Ubuntu Feminism is not only a critique of Western liberal feminism but also a reconstructive effort to root feminist thinking in African moral and philosophical traditions.

However, its focus on reconciliation and moral responsibility may risk underestimating the urgency of institutional reforms and structural change. While ethical appeals are important, they may not be sufficient to dismantle entrenched systems of power that sustain gender inequality. Furthermore,

¹⁷ Cornell, D. & Van Marle, K., 2015, "Ubuntu feminism: Tentative reflections", *Verbum et Ecclesia* 36(2), Art. #1444, 8 pages. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/ve.v36i2.1444>. p.2.

¹⁸ Cornell, D. & Van Marle, K., 2015, "Ubuntu feminism: Tentative reflections", *Verbum et Ecclesia* 36(2), Art. #1444, 8 pages. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/ve.v36i2.1444>. p.2.

Ubuntu Feminism's communal orientation may face tension in contexts where cultural norms continue to marginalize women's voices within the very communities it seeks to valorise. Nonetheless, Ubuntu Feminism offers a vital contribution to African feminist discourse. It affirms that true gender justice requires more than policy shifts; it involves a reorientation of societal values toward care, empathy, and collective accountability. In doing so, it reclaims and reframes indigenous knowledge for transformative feminist praxis.

9) Feminist Manifesto

In her work, *We Should All Be Feminists*, Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie introduces feminism through personal and cultural narratives, challenging patriarchal norms that reduce women's potential. She insists, "I matter. I matter equally. Full stop."¹⁹ For Adichie, feminism is not anti-male or Western, but a call for justice and dignity. In *Dear Ijeawele: A Feminist Manifesto in Fifteen Suggestions*,²⁰ Adichie writes to a friend who seeks advice on how to raise her daughter as a feminist.

1. Be a Full Person.

(Women must not let motherhood erase their identity. Girls must see their mothers living full, self-defined lives).

2. Do It Together.

(Parenting and domestic labour should be shared between partners. Equality starts at home).

3. Gender Roles Are Nonsense.

(Gender roles are socially constructed, not biologically ordained. Boys and girls are equally capable).

4. Beware of Feminism Lite.

(Avoid pseudo-feminist attitudes that offer superficial respect while reinforcing male dominance).

5. Teach Her to Read.

¹⁹ Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, *We Should All Be Feminists* (New York: Anchor Books, 2014), p. 26.

²⁰ Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, *Dear Ijeawele, or A Feminist Manifesto in Fifteen Suggestions* (New York: Knopf, 2017).

(Reading develops critical thinking and imagination, essential for personal and political empowerment).

6. Question Language.

(Language shapes perception. Avoid terms like “princess” that reinforce passivity or stereotype girls).

7. Marriage Is Not an Achievement.

(Do not raise girls to see marriage as their life goal. Teach them self-worth beyond romantic relationships).

8. Reject Likeability.

(Girls should not prioritize being liked over being authentic. Likeability often demands self-erasure).

9. Give Her a Sense of Identity.

(Instil pride in her heritage and teach her to critique cultural norms that harm women).

10. Engage Appearance Deliberately.

(Do not moralize beauty. Encourage healthy body image and activity, not self-shame or conformity).

11. Biology ≠ Destiny.

(Biological differences must not justify inequality. Social roles are not natural but constructed).

12. Talk Early About Sex.

(Sex education must be honest, shame-free, and empowering. Her body belongs to her alone).

13. Romance Will Happen.

(Teach girls that love must be mutual and never demand self-sacrifice at the expense of selfhood).

14. Don't Turn the Oppressed into Saints.

(Women need not be morally superior to deserve equality. Idealization is a form of erasure).

15. Teach Her About Differences.

(Diversity is a reality. Raise her to understand, respect, and navigate differences with empathy).

The above manifesto is not merely a parenting manual, but a transformative ethic, which encourages parents and caregivers to raise daughters who are confident, critical, and committed to justice. It reimagines motherhood as a practice of empowerment rather than self-sacrifice. However, Adichie's approach risks underplaying structural economic factors like class disparity that also shape women's oppression. Oyèrónké Oyěwùmí warns against universalizing Western gender categories across African contexts, urging deeper cultural specificity.²¹ Nonetheless, Adichie's work remains a notable contribution to contemporary thought.

ARE AFRICAN GENDER THEORISTS REAL FEMINISTS?

Examining the different African gender theories above offers one gender perspectives anchored on the African reality. A firm grasp of African orientation to gender relations and justice is proof that these erudite theorists know their onions, and should be respected for their perceptiveness, ingenuity, and commendable gender theories and manifesto. But who is a real feminist? If the insightful and committed gender theorists above are not real feminists, then they have no business answering feminists. If anyone deserves accolades for women's liberation, it must not be radical people who destroy the natural, disregard the supernatural, and disrupt social harmony worldwide. This calls to mind the monkeys that laugh when trees are felled, forgetting that the trees are their home. Opposing marriage and family, for instance, will have harmful effect on humanity, which feminists are part of. A river that forgets its source will dry up.

Surprisingly, the aforesaid African gender theorists declared and presented their theories as alternatives to Western feminism but failed to consider an alternative to "feminism" itself, even when they openly rejected and criticized the tenets and *modus operandi* of mainstream feminism (the parent body). One wonders, what ties them to that term? Could it be the phenomenon of who will bell the cat? Based on the philosophy of 'if you cannot beat them abstain', one expected a clean break with feminism, which would have left a legacy of strategies for maintaining independence and engagements as equals thereby

²¹ Oyèrónké Oyěwùmí, *The Invention of Women: Making an African Sense of Western Gender Discourses* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1997).

marking the end the narrative of inferiority and dependency, and resistance to inherent external pressure. Only Gynist philosophy stood out in this regard.

Multi polarity would enrich and not detract from the women's struggle. Just as humanity is individuated in persons like Peter, James, John, Ada, Ngozi, and Obi, the universe of gender discourse can be the same. Yet, Africans can still have a name that suits their unique standpoint on African women's concerns and the liberation of their Continent. This could be a way to emancipate African "feminism" from the apron string of Western feminism. In which case, there will be no more compulsion to follow the Western feminist established patterns and be recruited as their acolytes. After all, all the nations of the earth have different names, and yet they often meet for global summits. The term "African feminism" can be replaced with Gynism or *African Gender concerns*. Such insightful concerns can then be treated on our own terms without people being judgmental. Is prudence not said to be a greater part of valour? Our elders say: One who is not like others should never imitate others. Hence, it must be underscored that civil disobedience and demonstrations which enhanced the cause of feminism in the West are viewed askance in places like Nigeria where placards and peaceful protests often meet with hostility, police brutality, and even death in a democracy! Some of our foremothers paid the ultimate price at the Aba Riot quite alright, but if a repeat performance can be avoided, why not? Freedom is for the living. However, it must be mentioned that if at its core feminism is the belief that women deserve equal social, economic, and political rights and freedoms, then feminism has expired due to a fundamental shift. The fight now includes gay and transgendered persons, and not just women unlike womanism that included men *ab initio*.

GYNISM AS AN ALTERNATIVE TERM FOR AFRICAN FEMINISM

When a professor asked what the difference between Gynism and other African gender theories is, the response was: Gynism is a philosophy. Truly, apart from femocracy propounded by a psychologist, and ubuntu feminism written by two white philosophers, all the other African gender theories were formulated by literature scholars of African descent. Like life, which unfolds as we live it, Gynist philosophy expands as we excavate, analyze, and interrogate built-in emotive ideas incarnated in social praxis. Excavation exhumes irrefutable aspects of relegation relevant to the arguments that African men never marginalized their women. Thus, it is not a once-and-for-all made theory. Besides, Gynist philosophy transcends gender boundaries; it is all-embracing, just like philosophy itself.

Owing to feminist immoderations, Marie Pauline Eboh rejected the umbrella name “feminism” long ago and made bold to assert that she is not a feminist, even though she fights for women’s liberation. Gynism is apprised of the term woman as so inextricably tied to man, and female to male, that the entangling web does not allow the female reality to be defined except in function of male or man. Even though she aligns with Walker’s analysis of the woman question, Eboh could not accept the terms Womanism and femalism because they are shackled by the said androcentric web. Even m/other/ism has “other”-orientedness implicitly embedded in it. The import is that mother is built to be other-oriented, self-effacing, spend and be spent in the service of others. The inextricable androcentric web coupled with the awareness that “... words are often constructed from a male perspective”²² and most words that have to do with man are positive and respect-inducing e.g., **manager** and **chairman** unlike derogatory words derived from women and female, e.g., **womanizer** and **effeminate**. Ultimately, feminism was derived from *femina*, the Latin term for woman.

Thus, the term “Gynism” was devised in place of feminism to protest androcentric entanglement and feminist excesses. Gynism, fortunately, succeeds in addressing gender concerns, bypassing the androcentric web. Otherwise, it shares many principles in common with womanism and other African gender theories because African reality is the same and it is central to them all. Besides, African philosophy is relational and accommodationist love is a strong feature in African communalism. The peculiarity of Gynist philosophy consists mostly in its method of intuitive decomposition of words and linguistic expressions, exposition of structural injustices embedded in traditional practices, maxims, proverbs and innuendoes that undergird the denigration of women or deliberate deviation from the norm and logic of gender equity. For instance, the terms patrimony and matrimony are structured the same way. The only difference is “p” and “m”. These terms are derived from the Latin: *pater* (father) and *mater* (mother) respectively.²³ If so, where patrimony means “inheritance from a male ancestor”, logically, matrimony should automatically mean “inheritance from a female ancestor”, but it is not so. Why the deviation, and could this have anything to do with the exclusion of women from inheritance in some traditions? Why

²² M.P.Eboh, “Androcentric Web and Gynist Philosophy”. *Philosophical Criticisms: Anthology of Gender Issues* (Port Harcourt, Pearl Publishers, 2000), p. 24.

²³ M.P. Eboh, “Feminist Epistemology and Opinionated Dualism: The Way Forward”. *Philosophical Thought & Gynist Deconstruction of Gender* (Port Harcourt, Pearl Publishers International Ltd., 2015), p. 162

should matrimony mean marriage or a marriage ceremony? What is the logic behind it? Is marriage an inheritance from a female ancestor? Or is it only women that get married? Why should marriage be hung on a woman like a penchant?

We present Gynism to our universal audience as an alternative term or a substitute for “African Feminism”. This may seem ambitious, but it is already a sign of women liberation, having overcome the androcentric web, the entangling mesh which like a draconian dragnet gets woman more and more entangled the more she struggles to extricate and define herself because dignity goes with self-definition, and respect is earned through consistency. A cursory look at an intuitive decomposition of nouns and pronouns like **female**, **woman**, **she** and **herself** says it all; is it not amazing that “he” is there, even in woman’s self? This shows not only intrusiveness but how woman’s freedom is shackled from every facet of her reality. This is of great concern to Gynism. Women freedom fighting precludes a philosophy that is so abstract that it spells redundancy.

Gynist philosophy rests on nine pillars that serve as gender stepdown transformers or as implementation strategies. These pillars are intersecting principles of engagement. Some of them are quite common to other African and even Western gender theories because nothing human is alien to any culture.

1. Emancipatory Education

Emancipatory Education is critical and transformative. As we wrote elsewhere,

There is no gainsaying that the surest way out of women’s subjugation or servitude is individuals’ liberation through critical education. Women should, therefore, seek ways and means to acquire intellectual power to balance male/female mind power. When that is done, Moses will not need to beg Pharaoh to ‘let my people go.’²⁴

It is the type of education that asks not how a woman is but what a woman is, not how 2+3 is 5 but why 2+3 is 5? It makes people think deeply. It is not the kind that lets AI do the thinking and supply the answers. Most importantly, it aims at emancipating both men and women because men also need emancipation. Men’s inability to accord women equal status is due to psychological insecurity. Besides, some men are victims of domestic violence, and they are marginalized

²⁴ M.P. Eboh, *Philosophical Essays: Critique of Social Praxis*, (Port Harcourt, Paragraphics, 1996), p. 134.

in their families²⁵. They need help; they are hurting. Gynism does not replace male bias with female bias because two wrongs do not make a right, and the end does not justify the means, as Machiavelli says it does. That is why our Gynist Centre is open to men and women alike.

2. Gender dialogue

A preacher narrated this story, which I title *Allegory of Costly Silence*. It is the story of a couple that were not on talking terms for a long while. Consequently, the husband began to report late for work because his wife, who used to wake him up, stopped doing so as they did not talk to each other. He was warned that he would be sacked if he came late for work one more time. Instead of discussing the matter with his wife, he wrote her a note: "My wife, please wake me up at 5 am." He kept the note on her side of the bed. The wife saw the message when she woke up in the night to use the restroom. She equally wrote him a note: "My husband, wake up; it is time!" She kept the note on his side of the bed. Of course, he woke up late and consequently lost his job. This was detrimental to the entire family, for loss of job implies no salary, and therefore affects feeding money, house rent, children's school fees, etc. Dialogue could have forestalled these problems. If society prefers to silence women instead of discussing gender issues, people may continue to suffer unnecessarily, and there will be casualties on both sides of the gender divide.

3. Accommodationist love

As gregarious animals, humans need to cooperate. We adopt accommodationist love to refer to a relational ethic established on respect, complementarity, and mutual upliftment. It is not a passive surrender but a conscious act of embracing the other - male or female within the framework of dignity and shared humanity. This form of love fosters horizontal integration where each person's uniqueness is recognized and respected while working harmoniously with the other. It challenges patriarchal domination by promoting a space where both genders accommodate each other emotionally, intellectually, and socially. This approach bridges power imbalances and creates room for co-growth. In practical terms, accommodationist love is foundational to family cohesion, national unity, and ethical leadership. It is a love that listens, adjusts, and seeks harmony without erasing difference. Gynist Theory advances this love as a transformative energy of benevolence that sustains social justice and

²⁵ M.P. Eboh, *Witty Tales and Proverbs for Moral Renewal*, (Port Harcourt, Pearls Publishers International Ltd., 2015), p. 181.

cooperative progress. The goal is to reawaken goodwill, support, care, and benefaction in modern societies.

4. Complementarity

Our ideal metaphor for complementarity is the imagery of two physically challenged men on a mission, the blind and the lame. The blind carried the lame,²⁶ and the latter led the way. Who among them contributed more is immaterial? What matters is mission accomplished. As a Yoruba maxim puts it, if a man sees a snake and a woman kills it, the important thing is that the snake is killed. It is intriguing to note that Nigerian youths have inadvertently defined gender complementarity in a way. Neither bachelors nor spinsters are ready to marry anyone who has neither a job nor visible means of livelihood. Bodily beauty is no longer a ticket to reap where one did not sow. Nobody wants liabilities. The message is so clear that even after their degree(s), girls try to acquire entrepreneurial skills that can pay their bills. This is emancipatory because economic independence is the linchpin of women's emancipation. However, complementarity is much more than financial contribution. Men and women are analogous to the two hands of humanity; the right washes the left and the left washes the right, and this makes washing faster and cleaner.

Maraizu Elechi,²⁷ misunderstood the concept of complementarity, interpreting it as equal input and equality of personal achievements. To complement an academic husband, for instance, a wife does not need to contribute monthly resources that are equal to those of her husband or have a Ph.D. like his. However, if she has a Ph.D., it helps to balance mind power, enhance dialogue, and mutual respect. Her invaluable care, emotional labour, and house chores should count, even though domestic chores are not the preserve of women. Men should complement their wives in domesticity, especially now that most females are career women.

5. Harmony

Harmony is the balanced coexistence of differences without domination. It reflects a social and ethical ideal where gender, class, and cultural differences are recognized and integrated through dialogue and respect. In a society, a

²⁶ M. P. Eboh, "Two Famished People with Disabilities." *Fables, Proverbs & Critical Thinking*. (Port Harcourt, Pearl Publishers International Ltd., 2015), p. 185.

²⁷ M. Elechi, "Marie Pauline Eboh 's Gynist Theory: An Expository Analysis". In *Philosophy, Universal Dialogue and Intersectionality, Philosophical Essays in Honour of Marie Pauline Eboh*. M. Elechi & C. C.M.N Idika Ed., (Enugu, Rhyce Kerex Publishers, 2021), pp. 113-117.

successful blending of people and interests makes for peace. Gynist philosophy sees harmony not as uniformity but as a creative arrangement of diverse voices and roles in ways that strengthen the whole. It challenges power structures that exclude or silence women, and instead calls for horizontal relationships in which both men and women are active agents of peace and productivity. Harmony in this framework is a lived experience of equality-in-difference. Harmony is a goal of conflict resolution that cannot be attained without addressing issues properly and speaking truth to power. It is both a domestic and national imperative. For a Gynist thinker, a society without harmony is one where fragmentation, alienation, and injustice reign. Harmony is fostered by understanding, emotional intelligence, and ethical governance, making it essential for a truly inclusive world.

6. Mutual Respect

The axiom ‘Respect is reciprocal’ has not yet been faulted. Human dignity is an intrinsic value for all humans, male and female. Respect is a self-dignifying universal human principle. To be recognized and esteemed is a gratifying experience for men and women. Mutual respect is a foundational attribute of Gynism, tending to achieve gender equity, social integration, and integral human development. Mutual respect in the context of gender means men and women recognizing each other’s dignity, capabilities, and contributions to building a sustainable development without subordinating or silencing. In homes, institutions, and leadership, mutual respect sustains peace, reduces gender-based violence, and enables shared decision-making. It also nurtures a culture where emotional intelligence and dialogue replace competition and coercion. Thus, it is the bedrock of a just society where all individuals are honoured as *end in se*.

7. Gender Equity

Either by accident or by design, some men are averse to the expression “gender equality.” It tends to raise the level of their adrenaline. No two persons are mathematically equal; it is an undeniable fact that no two men are equal in intelligence, height, weight, handsomeness, or even financially. An Anambra person often says, “*Nwoke na ibe ya ra bu n’onu – That a man is equal to his neighbour is but mere parlance.*” Gender equality is formal; it is based on the principle that humans are born equal. They are made in the image and likeness of God – *imago Dei*. They are rational agents, and therefore, they are morally responsible for their actions and inactions. They have inalienable rights. Besides, gender equality implies equal opportunity for men and women. However, the

bird, *eleke ntioba*, said that since men have learnt to shoot without missing, it has learnt to fly without perching. Hence, emphasis has shifted to gender equity, which is gender justice: give each person, male or female, their due.

8. Care

Care is at the centre of Gynist vision for human and social development. Unlike the androcentric model that prioritizes abstract justice, Gynist ethics presents care as a relational and moral practice that affirms the worth of others and the existential need to reach out to them. Care here is not mere sentimentality and masked tokens of charity, but a principled commitment to well-being, healing, and the nurturing of potentials. It speaks to the responsibility to protect the vulnerable, value emotional labour, and build responsive institutions. In Gynist terms, care is both personal and political; it applies to the home, workplace, and governance structures. Thus, a society that fails to care fails to develop because it is a public good, requiring shared responsibility. Besides, in any given polity, the development of human capital should take precedence over infrastructural development. Care reflects a deeper moral wisdom that affirms interdependence and encourages empathetic policy decisions. In this way, care aligns with Gynist goals of gender justice, human flourishing, and inclusive transformation.

9. Environmental sustainability

Gynism extends its ethic of care and harmony to the environment by advocating for environmental sustainability rooted in the relational nature of being, an ontological nexus which we branded eco-synergy - a phenomenon that calls for relational responsibility. Just as the Gynist theory emphasizes mutual respect between genders, it also calls for respect for nature. The exploitation of the environment is seen as an extension of patriarchal logic that views nature, like women, as something to be dominated and consumed. Gynist ethics, by contrast, recognizes the earth as a life-giving partner that must be nurtured, cared for, and protected. It promotes sustainable living, eco-justice, and intergenerational responsibility. Eco-Gynism re-centres indigenous African cosmologies where humans, nature, and the supernatural are interconnected. A violation of the sacrosanct harmony between them is considered evil, and a desecration that must be restored by consecration. Environmental sustainability is a Gynist imperative redefining development beyond economic growth to include ecological balance, and zero tolerance for pollution globally. It aligns with the call for ethical transformation, showing that gender justice, human development, and

environmental care are inseparable in building a just, liveable, and healthy future for all.

CONCLUSION

As an appendage, African feminism *per se* suggests dependency. A woman dressed in borrowed wrapper does not dance freely. Stripped of mainstream revolutionary epistemic control, African feminism resorts to cultural specificities for authenticity. Its failure to endorse the universal feminists' *modus operandi* of responding to the denigration of women with *lex talionis*, bizarre practices, stark confrontation and violence also makes it a dissenting voice if not a rebel. Our elders say, instead of living manlike but behaving spirit-like, it is better to die and join the spirits to do as they do. Instead of the bat biting its catcher to death, it should be left to fly away.²⁸ Given the array of African theorists and a panoply of committed African women's liberation activists, who unrelentingly research, write, critique, enlighten, and engage in gender dialogue and awareness-raising, Africa is ready for a befitting, unique movement of her own naming. It is not easy to be a child of two worlds, sacrificing autonomy and self-definition to conventionality. Instead of universal feminism costing African her values, and further erosion of dignity, shouldn't the nametag, "feminism" be dropped? After all, the African theorists above presented their gender theories not as adjuncts but as alternatives to Western feminism. Thus, an alternative movement is not ruled out. A new template for engagement is called for. But whatever happens, the establishment of *African Gender Ethics* is necessary and urgent to contain feminist excesses.

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²⁸ M.P. Eboh, *The Structure of Igbo Logic as Shown in Dispute Settlement* (Port Harcourt, Pearl Publishers, 2014), p. 127.